

IMPLEMENTATION OF PERSONNEL POLICY IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article is devoted to priority areas in training competitive specialists for the country's oil and gas industry. Particular attention is paid to the quality of education at the university, the implementation of the dual interconnectedness of theory and practice, the introduction of advanced international requirements, the transfer of innovative knowledge and technologies to the country's fuel energy sector.

Key words: education, upbringing, competitive specialist, innovation, advanced technology.

РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ КАДРОВОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена приоритетным направлениям в подготовке конкурентоспособных специалистов для нефтегазовой отрасли страны. Особое внимание уделено качеству образования в вузе, реализации дуальной взаимосвязанности теории и практики, внедрению передовых международных требований, трансфера инновационных знаний и технологий в топливную энергетику страны.

Ключевые слова: образование, воспитание, конкурентоспособный специалист, инновации, передовые технологии.

INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions of development, large-scale democratic reforms are being implemented at a dynamic pace in Uzbekistan, aimed at strengthening our state and society in all spheres, modernizing the country, strengthening the role of parliament and political parties, and public control in this process. Particular attention is paid to

ensuring human rights and legitimate interests, freedom of speech and religion - the main principles of democracy. In order to further implement the assigned tasks, the main life idea was determined – «In the name of a new life, in the name of New Uzbekistan!»²³, reflecting the main priority directions of development of Uzbekistan until 2026.

Of particular note are reforms in the education sector. In his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 20, 2022, the head of state emphasized that «The key to prosperity is in education, upbringing, knowledge. For all good goals are achieved through knowledge and education». In recent years, the number of universities in the country has increased 2.5 times - to 198, and enrollment in higher education has increased from 9 to 38 percent. 41 universities have received academic and financial independence; transformation offices have been opened in them, where teachers are widely introducing new, advanced teaching methods.

Today, proactive and devoted youth with independent and innovative thinking and a sense of responsibility are achieving world-class results in various fields and areas. Modern knowledge and achievement of progress, determination and dedicated work will become the basis for building a New Uzbekistan and forming the foundation of the Third Renaissance in the country [1]. In the current conditions of development, comprehensive, complete knowledge, high intelligence, and personal resources of talented youth are important.

LITERATURE AND METHODOLOGY.

The main task of the Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas named after I.M. Gubkin in the city of Tashkent is the training of highly qualified specialists for the oil and gas industry of the republic in accordance with the educational programs adopted at the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) named after I.M. Gubkin and generally recognized international requirements for the quality of higher education, the goals and objectives of the National Program for Personnel Training of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Branch is a separate structural unit of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) named after I.M. Gubkin, a higher educational institution aimed at training specialists at all levels, including the training of scientific and pedagogical personnel. Its activities are carried out in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation.

Practical observations indicate that the admission of applicants and certification of graduates of the Branch are carried out in accordance with the requirements, procedures and deadlines established by the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) named after I.M. Gubkin. Training at the Branch is carried out according to

²³ Welcoming speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan at the celebrations dedicated to the national holiday Navruz, March 22, 2024, No. 59 (8637) / https://tsue.uz/media/uploads/2024/03/25/1-4_NSZ27GI.pdf.

curricula and programs approved by the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) named after I.M. Gubkina.

A standard diploma issued to graduates of the Branch on graduation from the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (NRU) named after I.M. Gubkin is recognized as a document on higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Graduates who studied on the basis of state grants are subject to assignment to work, with the condition of working for at least three years at enterprises and organizations of the oil and gas industry of the republic.

The results of the analysis indicate that the Branch is rightfully proud of its graduates working in all oil and gas companies operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Today the Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas named after I.M. Gubkina is a modern, comfortable for learning and working bilingual Branch with a close-knit team of highly qualified specialists, providing in-demand and high-quality educational and scientific services, using advanced technologies, with a high level of youth self-organization and international activity²⁴.

The Branch is a supplier of highly qualified personnel in demand from leading companies in the oil and gas industry of the republic and abroad, demanding employers who attract leading personnel from educational institutions, industry companies, as well as high-tech research centers to production.

RESULTS.

The priority objectives of the Branch are improving educational programs, attracting and recruiting talented applicants, increasing the level and volume of research activities of students, attracting and developing key university personnel, developing infrastructure and laboratory facilities, integrating science, education and production.

The main mission of the Branch is to train a new generation of competent and competitive specialists for the oil and gas industry of the republic, taking into account advanced international requirements, the formation, development and transfer of innovative knowledge and technologies in the oil and gas sector by ensuring high quality of the educational process, research work and high-tech developments. In a word, the Branch sees its strategic goal as becoming the flagship of innovative development of the oil and gas industry, relying on the unity of the triad «education - science - production» [2].

DISCUSSION

As a result of the work carried out, the Branch has turned into a basic multi-purpose cluster that provides training for future personnel for the sustainable development of the country's oil and gas industry. At the same time, the tasks of

²⁴ Usmanova A.A. The power of new reforms in Uzbekistan is in the name of human interests / Newspaper "Pravda Vostoka", No. 56 dated March 19, 2024.

creating a spiritual and moral environment that contributes to the education of harmoniously developed youth with stable views on life, a strong civic position, capable of realizing their physical and intellectual potential for the benefit of the country's development are being updated.

At the same time, priority is also given to efforts aimed at improving the level of education by attracting talented applicants from various regions of the republic, as well as foreign countries, developing a system of pre-university targeted training, creating a portfolio of educational programs, standards and curricula of the modern generation, developing professional potential teaching staff, widespread introduction of modern information technologies and distance learning, raising the level of research and applied activities of the university through the introduction of advanced scientific schools in leading areas of science and technology in the oil and gas industry.

One of the tools for increasing the competitiveness of the personnel training system for high-tech production is the dual education system, the advantage of which is the close integration of education and production. Dual education fully complies with the basic principles of the competency-based approach, based on the educational standards of modern professional education.

Since the beginning of 2021, the Branch has been using a dual education system. 3rd and 4th year students in the areas of study «Geological exploration technology», «Drilling oil and gas wells», «Operation and maintenance of oil production facilities», «Operation and maintenance of gas production facilities, gas condensate and underground storage facilities», «Operation and maintenance of transport and storage facilities for oil, gas and refined products», «Construction and repair of gas and oil pipelines and gas and oil storage facilities», under the guidance of leading production specialists, they strengthen their theoretical knowledge in practice and learn the secrets of the profession, master the basics and acquire the skills of their future profession at oil and gas enterprises industries of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Field trips provide opportunities for students to immerse themselves in a professional environment and experience real-life work in the oil and gas industry, while practical experience allows students to apply theoretical knowledge gained in their studies to real-life problems and situations.

In addition, familiarity with production processes within the framework of dual education helps students see the chain of creation of a product or service from beginning to final result. In turn, understanding production processes allows students to evaluate the efficiency of the enterprise, identify bottlenecks and propose improvements to optimize production.

As was emphasized by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev: «The solution to all our problems, the answers to all questions are only

in education. The key that opens all doors is education and upbringing»²⁵. Our priority areas remain the formation of deep personalities striving for modern, ambitious knowledge, creative skills and key professional skills.

The Branch is proud of its success in the field of effective interaction between mentoring experience and educational programs aimed at growing the intellectual potential of each student and training in-demand specialists in the labor market of Uzbekistan. Such symbiosis is the most important prerequisite for improving the quality of the educational process, creating fundamentally new conditions for research and educational work of teachers and students, and increasing the volume of implementation of educational program opportunities in production models.

Launched at the Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas (scientific research university) named after I.M. Gubkin in the city of Tashkent, the internship program is a vivid example of comprehensive support for an effective system of strategic partnerships between the Branch and production associations, which, in turn, help create fertile ground for graduates to start working.

In this regard, within the framework of cooperation with manufacturing enterprises, the Branch has been carrying out targeted work for many years on the formation of modern specialists for the oil and gas industry of Uzbekistan. Close partnerships have been established with such leading industrial production of Uzbekneftegaz JSC, Bukhara Oil Refinery LLC, Shurtan Gas Chemical Plant LLC, Mubarek Gas Processing Plant, Fergana Oil Refinery LLC, Lukoil Uzbekistan Operating Company LLC, Eriell Oilfield Services Middle East DMCC, Enter Engineering PTE Ltd, Uzbekistan GTL LLC, JSC «Uztransgaz», LLC «GRDC», LLC «Sanoat Enegetika Guruhi» (SANEG), FDI Uzlit Engineering LLC, Khududgaztaminot JSC, TsPT under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, Ministry of Economy and Finance, State Institution IGIRNIGM, Uzbekgeofizika JSC.

The Branch sees the main goal of integration in ensuring the interconnection and interdependence of educational and production processes, attracting teachers and teachers to actively participate in joint innovative research, effectively use the experimental resource base of enterprises to train future in-demand specialists who can work productively in the field of processing oil and gas products for various industries of the country.

The interests of the Branch are aimed at fundamental research on the extraction of fuel energy in Uzbekistan, bringing educational laboratory facilities as close as possible to international standards, attracting the necessary material resources to attract students and partner enterprises in the development of current projects to

²⁵ Speech by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the ceremony dedicated to the 33rd anniversary of the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan / <https://president.uz/ru/lists/view/7519>.

improve methods of production, processing and use of oil and gas in enterprises and organizations of the republic on the basis of mutual usefulness.

Integration of the Branch with production associations implies the introduction into practice of various forms and methods of the innovation process aimed at the duration of educational programs for training future specialists for the oil and gas industry. As part of the internship program, the Branch's teachers conduct a number of meetings and training seminars. Participants are provided with video materials about the life and activities of the university, innovative projects and student start-ups dedicated to advanced technologies for the extraction and processing of oil and gas in the republic. The advantage of the programs is the integration of the educational process and industrial practice. Such a need to update the interconnectedness of theoretical knowledge and teaching practice in the Branch, where teaching should serve one of the noble goals - the formation of highly qualified specialists for the oil and gas industry of the country, highly cultural and sought-after young people - a reliable support of the New Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION.

The youth policy implemented in the Branch is a fruitful platform for training and forming a personnel reserve in the oil and gas industry. For these purposes, there is a student scientific community, whose activities are aimed at the comprehensive development of the scientific potential of student youth. At the initiative of students, events are regularly held aimed at obtaining new scientific knowledge and developing professional skills. In the 2023-2024 academic year alone, students won more than 12 medals at international competitions. At the same time, more than 300 articles were published, 15 students became owners of state and personal scholarships.

In addition, for the further sustainable development of the Branch, effective tools and technologies for personnel management, improvement of the educational infrastructure in accordance with the best best practices, provision of high IT services, activities of the information resource center, and creation of favorable conditions for the life of students and teachers become important.

The future tasks of the Branch are related to the further strengthening of the leading innovative position of one of the leaders of the country's educational institutions in obtaining quality education, its competitiveness among other universities in the country. This will undoubtedly make it possible to achieve positive growth in the production of oil and gas products in Uzbekistan and popularize the image of the country's fuel energy industry in the international arena. Graduates will be able to implement their acquired professional competencies in the industry labor market, apply their potential to achieve stable growth in incomes and improve the well-being of our people.

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